

ISic0770

Dedication by Marcus Aimilius Rho[--]

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Contributors

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-08 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based on work for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found lying on the floor of the first room of the north side of the west portico (agora); the stone fits perfectly into a niche in the original wall of the room above where it was found, that is 1.8m above the floor and measures 0.25 x 0.37 x 0.07-0.10 m (a plaster-cast of the stone is currently displayed in its place).

Coordinates

37.998116, 14.262650

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20223

Physical Description

Part of a small rectangular slab, of a compact white limestone. The lower right of the slab is lost, including all of the right side and most of the lower edge. The rear of the slab is smoothly finished.

Dimensions

Height 21 cm

Width 27 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

The first part of all six lines of the Greek text are preserved, but none are complete.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are uniform and well cut, with pronounced serifs. A hollow triangular interpunct is used between all the onomastic elements (but apparently not elsewhere in the text; spaces are however observed between words, with or without interpunct). Theta has a detached middle bar; omicron is full size; epsilon has a detached short middle bar; mu reaches almost to the lower line in the middle, and the outer strokes are vertical.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 15 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. θεοῖς πᾶσι

2. Μ(άρκος) · Αἰμίλιος · Ρό[δων]

3. Κίππου · υἱὸς · ὑπ[ὲρ τῆς]
4. ἀγορανομ[ίας]
5. ἀνέθ[ηκεν]
6. ἐκ τῶ[ν ἰδίων]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Markos Aimilios Rhodon, son of Kipos dedicated (this) to all the gods at his own expense in commemoration of his aedileship.

Commentary

Scibona (1971) [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/UISW82JC>] and Manganaro (1988) [<http://zotero.org/groups/382445/items/RZSFKACR>] speculated on how best to restore the ends of lines 2 and 3, but Moretti (1986-1987) [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/FMWK9VN3>] offered a convincing solution (adopted here). Moretti noted that the placing of the patronymic in full after the complete Roman tria nomina is relatively common among new Roman citizens in the first century BC (Marcus' father was clearly not a Roman citizen, having the Oscan name Kipos, which is attested, e.g., in the Entella tablets). The gens Aemilia is well attested in Sicily, including several Roman magistrates (see Facella 2006: 277-278 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/J4XWZPV6>]), but one cannot simply assume that Rhodon was given citizenship by a Roman magistrate bearing the name Marcus Aemilius, as patterns of practice in this regard have been shown to be very irregular (see e.g. Pina Polo, F. 2015. Foreign clientelae revisited: a methodological critique, in F. Pina Polo and M. Jehne (eds), *Foreign Clientelae in the Roman Empire: A Reconsideration*, Stuttgart: Franz Steiner: 19-42). The text makes it explicit that Rhodon made the dedication to mark his holding of the office of agoranomos, (aedile) a magistrate responsible for management of the city's buildings and markets and so the agora in particular (see Fantasia, U. 2012. I magistrati dell'agora nelle città greche di età classica ed ellenistica. In C. Ampolo (ed.), *Agora greca e agorai di Sicilia* (Pisa: Edizioni della Normale), 31-56.). The text does not make explicit what it was that he dedicated, but since the stone appears to have been mounted as a plaque on the wall, rather than serving as a statue base, it is most likely that he restored or improved part or all of the building in which it was found (Campagna 2007 [<http://zotero.org/groups/382445/items/U69VG3A2>]).

The text cannot be securely dated. The style of the letters suggests a date at the end of the Hellenistic period, although the Greek text suggests we are still in the first century BC and probably before the Augustan period. It is worth

noting that the one other example of triangular interpuncts of this particular form at Halaesa is in a dedication to Augustus ISic0582 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0582>] , although this is recorded only in the antiquarian tradition.

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